

Supplementary Materials for “Continuous Ankle Motion Prediction from Bi-Channel EMG Signals: A Hybrid BWO-FAWT and GRU Approach”

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This document contains online supplementary materials complementing the main article entitled: “Continuous Ankle Motion Prediction from Bi-Channel EMG Signals: A Hybrid BWO-FAWT and GRU Approach”. It includes additional figures, detailed tables, and appendixes that could not be included in the printed version due to space limitations. For the main text, please refer to the published paper.

1. Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: The flow diagram of dataset preparation.

Figure S2: GRU model structure.

Figure S3: Time domain waveform of original (Top) and denoised EMG signal (Bottom).

Figure S4: Prediction results through variable walking speed.

2. Supplementary Tables

Table S1: Evaluation of GRU model thorough variable subjects and walking speed.

Speed\Subject	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 3	Subject 4	Subject 5	Mean	
RMSE (°) MAE (°) R2	0.5 km/h	1.1716 0.9343 0.9589	1.1684 0.9295 0.9571	1.3430 1.0575 0.9660	1.0319 0.8317 0.9707	1.1874 0.9555 0.9594	1.1805 0.9417 0.9624
	1 km/h	1.2664 1.0354 0.9432	1.0692 0.8484 0.9702	1.0658 0.8499 0.9711	1.1603 0.9312 0.9619	1.1981 0.9718 0.9596	1.1520 0.9273 0.9612
	1.5 km/h	1.2413 1.0179 0.9499	1.0694 0.8289 0.9773	0.9598 0.7749 0.9766	1.3023 1.0385 0.9447	1.1981 0.9718 0.9596	1.1542 0.9264 0.9616
	2 km/h	1.0890 0.8817 0.9668	1.0593 0.8311 0.9790	0.9798 0.7961 0.9793	1.2612 1.0127 0.9525	1.2069 0.9598 0.9554	1.1192 0.8963 0.9666
	2.5 km/h	1.2449 1.0178 0.9550	1.1980 0.9172 0.9772	0.9218 0.7320 0.9801	1.1501 0.9085 0.9622	1.3063 1.0544 0.9495	1.1642 0.9260 0.9648
	3 km/h	1.1258 0.8887 0.9656	1.1778 0.9453 0.9790	1.0014 0.7815 0.9757	1.0497 0.8239 0.9780	1.0506 0.8285 0.9710	1.0811 0.8536 0.9739
	3.5 km/h	1.2999 1.0529 0.9449	1.2070 0.9560 0.9796	1.1500 0.9007 0.9710	1.1406 0.8807 0.9776	1.0722 0.8320 0.9781	1.1739 0.9245 0.9702
	4 km/h	1.2584 1.0167 0.9492	1.2800 1.0319 0.9804	0.9785 0.7814 0.9769	1.2749 0.9999 0.9681	1.0724 0.8334 0.9795	1.1728 0.9327 0.9708
	4.5 km/h	1.4418 1.1710 0.9119	1.4049 1.1567 0.9769	1.1015 0.8489 0.9790	1.4435 1.1931 0.9767	1.2314 0.9765 0.9771	1.3246 1.0692 0.9643
	5 km/h	1.3447 1.0780 0.9457	1.4348 1.1800 0.9768	1.0838 0.8556 0.9810	1.3522 1.0962 0.9782	1.1973 0.9541 0.9805	1.2826 1.0328 0.9724
Mean	1.2484 1.0094 0.9491	1.2069 0.9625 0.9754	1.0585 0.8379 0.9757	1.2167 0.9716 0.9671	1.1721 0.9338 0.9670		

Table S1 – Detailed parameters of the ANN model and controller settings.

Table S2 – Full numerical results (RMSE, MAE) for all tested scenarios.

3. Supplementary Appendixes

Appendix A

A.1. Gated Recurrent Unit-based

GRUs are a recurrent neural network architecture known for its efficiency in processing sequential data, particularly in time-series forecasting. They excel in handling multivariate time-series data, enabling the learning of complex interdependencies and patterns, making them a powerful tool for accurate and reliable joint movement prediction from sEMG signals.

Figure 12: GRU cell, reset gate in the red box and update gate in the blue one.

At each time step t , the GRU cell updates its hidden state h_t based on the input x_t and the previous hidden state h_{t-1} . The GRU performs these updates through the following steps (Figure 12):

- **Update gate (z_t):** The update gate determines the extent to which the previous hidden state h_{t-1} should be carried forward to the current hidden state.

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z \cdot x_t + U_z \cdot h_{t-1} + b_z) \quad (21)$$

With σ is the Sigmoid activation function, W_z and U_z are weight matrices for the input and hidden state, and b_z represents the bias vector.

- **Reset gate (r_t):** The reset gate determines how much of the previous hidden state h_{t-1} should be ignored.

$$r_t = \sigma(W_r \cdot x_t + U_r \cdot h_{t-1} + b_r) \quad (22)$$

With W_r and U_r are weight matrices for the input and hidden state, and b_r represents the bias vector.

- **Candidate Hidden State (\tilde{h}_t):** The candidate hidden state represents the new content to be added to the current hidden state.

$$\tilde{h}_t = \tanh(W_h \cdot x_t + r_t \odot (U_h \cdot h_{t-1}) + b_h) \quad (23)$$

With W_h and U_h are weight matrices for the input and hidden state, b_h represents the bias vector, and \odot is the element-wise multiplication.

- **Final Hidden State (h_t):** The final hidden state is a linear interpolation between the previous hidden state and the candidate hidden state, controlled by the update gate.

$$h_t = z_t \odot h_{t-1} + (1 - z_t) \odot \tilde{h}_t \quad (24)$$

Appendix B

B.1. FAWT: Flexible Analytic Wavelet Transform (formulations)

The FAWT is applied to the signal $x_b(t)$, where $x_b(t)$ is the input sEMG signal of length L . The FAWT uses a combination of low-pass and high-pass filters defined by the parameters p , q , r , s to decompose and denoise $x_b(t)$ in the frequency domain.

To analyze $x_b(t)$ in the frequency domain, the normalized Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is first applied:

$$X_b(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L}} \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} x_b(n) e^{-jn\omega}, \quad 0 \leq \omega < 2\pi \quad (25)$$

Where, n represents the time index, L is the signal length, j is the imaginary unit, and ω is the frequency variable.

The frequency domain signal $X_b(\omega)$ is decomposed into low-frequency and high-frequency components. The decomposition at layer J is expressed as:

$$X_b(\omega) = D_b^J(\omega) + \sum_{x=1}^{2^J} \mu_{bx}, \quad J \geq 1 \quad (26)$$

where:

- $D_b^J(\omega)$: Low-frequency component at the J^{th} layer.
- μ_{bx} : High-frequency components selected by the high-pass filter with $x = 1, 2, \dots, 2^J$.

For a given decomposition level $J > 1$, the low-frequency component $D_{by}(\omega)$ at layer y is recursively defined as:

$$D_{by}(\omega) = D_{b1} \left(\left(\frac{p}{q} \right)^{y-1} \omega \right) \prod_{m=0}^{y-2} \frac{1}{p} L \left(\left(\frac{p}{q} \right)^m \frac{\omega}{p} \right), \quad y = 2, 3, \dots, J \quad (27)$$

where:

- p : Up-sampling factor.
- q : Down-sampling factor.
- $L(\omega)$: Low-pass filter response.

The low-frequency component at the first layer is given by:

$$D_b^1(\omega) = X_b(\omega)L(\omega) \quad (28)$$

The frequency response of the low-pass filter $L(\omega)$ is defined as:

$$L(\omega) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{pq} & \text{when } |\omega| < \omega_p \\ \sqrt{pq}\phi\left(\frac{\omega - \omega_p}{\omega_s - \omega_p}\right) & \text{when } \omega_p \leq \omega \leq \omega_s \\ \sqrt{pq}\phi\left(\frac{\pi - \omega + \omega_p}{\omega_s - \omega_p}\right) & \text{when } -\omega_s \leq \omega \leq -\omega_p \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

Where:

- $\phi(\cdot)$: Smoothing function for the transition band.
- ω_p : Passband frequency given as: $\omega_p = \frac{(1-\beta)\pi}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon}{\pi}$.
- ω_s : Stopband frequency defined as: $\omega_s = \frac{\pi}{q}$.
- β and ε are positive constants defined under the following constraints: $1 - \frac{p}{q} \leq \beta \leq \frac{r}{s}$ and $\varepsilon \leq \pi \left(\frac{p-q+\beta q}{p+q}\right)$.

The smoothing function $\phi(\omega)$ is defined as:

$$\phi(\omega) = \frac{1 + \cos(\omega)\sqrt{2 - \cos(\omega)}}{2}, \quad 0 \leq \omega \leq \pi \quad (30)$$

The frequency response of the high-pass filter $H(\omega)$ is defined as:

$$H(\omega) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{rs}\phi\left(\frac{\pi - \omega - \omega_0}{\omega_1 - \omega_0}\right) & \text{when } \omega_0 \leq \omega \leq \omega_1 \\ \sqrt{rs} & \text{when } \omega_1 < \omega \leq \omega_2 \\ \sqrt{rs}\phi\left(\frac{\omega - \omega_2}{\omega_3 - \omega_2}\right) & \text{when } \omega_2 < \omega \leq \omega_3 \\ 0 & \text{when } \omega \in [0, \omega_0) \cup (\omega_3, 2\pi) \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

Where, $\omega_0, \omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3$ are defined based on the sampling factors r and s as follow: $\omega_0 = \frac{(1-\beta)\pi + \varepsilon}{r}$, $\omega_1 = \frac{p\pi}{qr}$, $\omega_2 = \frac{\pi - \varepsilon}{r}$, and $\omega_3 = \frac{\pi + \varepsilon}{r}$.

The denoised signal $\tilde{x}_b(t)$ is reconstructed from the decomposed frequency domain components $X_b(\omega)$ using the inverse Fourier transform:

$$\tilde{x}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L}} \sum_{\omega=0}^{L-1} X_b(\omega) e^{jt\omega} \quad (32)$$

B.2. BWO: Black Widow Optimization (formulations)

The algorithm begins with an initial population of P candidate solutions randomly distributed in the search space. During each generation, reproduction occurs between pairs of solutions (parents), generating offspring solutions according to a predefined crossover probability p_c . Subsequently, a proportion of the weaker offspring, determined by a cannibalism rate r_c , is eliminated to maintain the population size and enforce selective survival. The remaining offspring are evaluated for fitness, and the best-performing solutions are retained for the next generation. Overall, the algorithm consists of the following steps:

- Initializing a population of candidate solutions randomly distributed within the defined search space:

$$\mathbf{S} = \{s^{(1)}, s^{(2)}, \dots, s^{(P)}\}, \quad s_j^{(i)} \in [s_{j,\min}, s_{j,\max}], \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (33)$$

Where: \mathbf{S} is the population of solutions, $s^{(i)} = (s_1^{(i)}, s_2^{(i)}, \dots, s_n^{(i)})$ represents the i -th candidate solution, n is the dimensionality of the search space, P is the population size, and $[s_{j,\min}, s_{j,\max}]$ defines the bounds for the j -th dimension of the search space.

- Evaluating each candidate solution $s^{(i)}$ using the objective function:

$$F^{(i)} = f(s^{(i)}), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, P \quad (34)$$

Where: $F^{(i)}$ is the fitness of the i -th solution and $f(s)$ is the objective function to minimize.

- Generating new offspring solutions by combining two parent solutions $s^{(p_1)}$ and $s^{(p_2)}$ chosen from the population:

$$s_j^{(child)} = \alpha \cdot s_j^{(p_1)} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot s_j^{(p_2)}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (35)$$

Where: $s^{(child)}$ is the offspring solution, $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a random weight determining the contribution of each parent to the offspring, and j indexes the dimensions of the solution vector.

- Proceeding to the offspring mutation to introduce diversity by perturbing a randomly selected dimension:

$$s_j^{(mutated)} = s_j^{(child)} + \beta \cdot (s_{j,\max} - s_{j,\min}), \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (36)$$

Where: $s_j^{(mutated)}$ represents the j -th mutated solution dimension and β is a small random value typically drawn from a uniform or Gaussian distribution.

- Eliminating the weakest offspring fraction r_c based on fitness:

$$S_{next} = \text{SelectBest}(S_{current}, F_{current}, r_c) \quad (37)$$

Where: S_{next} is the updated population, SelectBest is a function that retains the best solutions based on fitness values $F_{current}$, and r_c is the cannibalism rate.

- Stopping the algorithm when a termination criterion is met.